

Metal ion recognition : A fluorene-based podand for the selective detection of Hg²⁺ ion[†]

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Abstract : Fluorene-based fluorescent chemosensor 1 has been reported here for the selective sensing of Hg²⁺. Chemosensor 1 effectively binds Hg²⁺ (20 μM level) in aqueous acetonitrile medium (10 : 1 v/v) using HEPES buffer (pH 7.0) among the other metal ions (Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ba²⁺, Pb²⁺, Fe³⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Mn²⁺) considered for the study.

Keywords : Fluorene-based chemosensor, Hg²⁺ sensing, CHEQ effect.

Introduction

The development of receptors for the selective sensing of biologically and environmentally important species has drawn great attention¹⁻⁴ and becomes one of the rapidly growing research topics of interest in recent years. Many sensors have been designed for the selective detection of soft and heavy transition metal ions Hg²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺, Cu²⁺ etc.⁵⁻¹⁴. Among the heavy toxic metal ions and environmentally hazardous contaminants, mercury plays the role of one of the most important great leaders in biological and environmental pollutions. This toxic heavy metal can affect human life and ecology at very low concentration limit. Both elemental and ionic mercury can be converted to methyl mercury by environmental bacteria and subsequent accumulation occurs smoothly through the food chain¹⁵⁻¹⁹. In the case of aquatic systems, mercury generally accumulates mostly in the upper levels, especially in the large edible fishes and other marine mammals¹⁵⁻¹⁹ and thus mercury can easily get transferred into the human body. The major concerns regarding mercury poisoning include Hg²⁺-induced brain damage (central nervous system), DNA damage, various cognitive and motion disorders including damage of mitosis and endocrine system and last but not the least is

Minamata disease²⁰⁻²⁶. Mercury contamination can also take place through a variety of natural and soft metal anthropogenic sources including volcanic emission, gold mining, solid waste incineration, and combustion of fossil fuels²⁷.

Many techniques e.g. atomic absorption spectroscopy^{28,29}, inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy^{30,31}, electrochemistry³² and cold-vapor atomic fluorescence³³ have recently been used for the detection of mercury. But these are highly costly. Therefore, design of sensors which can selectively recognize mercury is of great challenge³⁴⁻⁴⁹. The design of fluorescent chemosensors is one of the active fields of molecular recognition and supramolecular chemistry. It has potential practical benefits in cell physiology, analytical and environmental chemistry⁵⁰. It also has applications for the manipulation of various photophysical processes for the design of selective sensor for tailor-made molecular or ionic species^{51,52}.

Compared to the sensors designed for Hg²⁺, fluorescence offers proving ground by providing simplicity and high sensitivity which translates molecular recognition into tangible fluorescence signals^{1,2}. Recently, many receptors were designed for the selective sensing of Hg²⁺

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which include hydroxyquinolines, cyclams, dioxocyclams, diaza tetrathia crown ethers, azines, diaza-crown ethers, nitrobenzo oxadiazolyl moieties, fluorescein, rhodamine, 1,8-naphthalimide, cyanin⁵³⁻⁵⁸ etc. Thus an overview of these receptors reveals the secret that mainly the nitrogen and sulfur atoms present within the ionophore promotes the binding of mercury ions. We report here fluorene-based sulfur and nitrogen containing half-crown, chemosensor **1** for the selective detection of Hg^{2+} in acetonitrile- H_2O (10 : 1 v/v) mixture. Receptor **1** selectively binds Hg^{2+} in aqueous acetonitrile mixture by turn-off process due to chelation enhanced fluorescence quenching (CHEQ) mechanism^{44,48,49}.

The chemosensor **1** has been synthesized from the well known starting material 9-fluorenone by imine formation reaction with ethanolamine, followed by borohydride reduction and tosylation to afford intermediate **C** (Scheme 1) which then underwent reaction with dithiol to produce the desired receptor **1** in ~70% yield.

Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions : (i) ethanolamine, dry EtOH, reflux, 1 h; (ii) NaBH_4 , dry MeOH, r.t., 2 h; (iii) *p*-TsCl, dry Et_3N , dry CH_2Cl_2 , 0 °C, 14 h; (iv) 1,3-propanedithiol, NaOEt, dry EtOH, r.t, 3 h.

The surveyed receptor **1** exhibited characteristic absorption band at $\lambda_{\text{max}} \sim 292$ nm with shoulders at ~ 283 nm, 307 nm, 323 nm and 380 nm in HEPES buffered aqueous acetonitrile solution (pH 7.0, 10 mM) (Fig. 1). Upon treatment with Hg^{2+} ions, the absorption bands mentioned earlier gradually decreased and a new band appeared at ~ 364 nm. Other metal ions induced some

variation in absorbance without any marked change in absorption maximum. The perchlorate salts of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Hg^{2+} ions were used here for the evaluation of metal-binding properties of receptor **1**. K_{α} determined^{62,63} by UV method (Fig. 2) of **1** and Hg^{2+} is $1.29 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$.

The stoichiometry of complexation has been assumed to be 1 : 1 from the binding graph (Fig. 2a) and confirmed by the Job plot (Fig. 2b) determined by UV-Vis method.

The fluorescence spectra were obtained by excitation of the fluorene fluorophore at 292 nm. Compound **1** exhibits selective ON-OFF signaling behavior towards Hg^{2+} determined by fluorescence method in aqueous acetonitrile solutions and shows a marked change in presence of Hg^{2+} compared to the other cations studied (Fig. 5), e.g. Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Cu^{2+} . Among

these, metal ion receptor showed large fluorescence quenching only with Hg^{2+} (Fig. 3) even though there was relatively smaller fluorescence quenching with Cu^{2+} . Receptor **1** has its λ_{max} concentrated at 518 nm with shoulder at 575 nm. Due to addition of Hg^{2+} ion gradual decrease of the band intensity at 518 nm takes place. But the change of intensity of the band at 575 nm is quite

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra of receptor 1 in the presence of Hg^{2+} ion in $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (10 : 1 v/v) at pH 7.0 (10 mM HEPES buffer). $[\text{1}] = 1.92 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Hg}^{2+}] = 6.88 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.

Fig. 3. Change of fluorescence intensity of receptor 1 due to addition of Hg^{2+} ion as its perchlorate salt in HEPES buffer solution (pH 7.0, 10 mM).

Fig. 2. (a) Plot of change of absorbance vs ratio of concentration of guest $[\text{G}]$ and concentration of host $[\text{H}]$; (b) Job plot of receptor 1 and Hg^{2+} determined by UV-Vis method.

irregular resulting ultimately $\sim 70\%$ fluorescence quenching in total (Fig. 4c), i.e. 'switching-off' due to the formation of cation-host complex. The 1 : 1 stoichiometry was also confirmed by the Job plot^{62,63} (Fig. 4b). K_a

determined⁵⁹⁻⁶¹ by fluorescence method between 1 and Hg^{2+} is found to be $1.04 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$.

MM2 optimized⁶⁴⁻⁶⁷ structures of receptor 1 and its complex with Hg^{2+} have been shown in Fig. 6. This structure shows the mode of binding of receptor 1 with Hg^{2+} .

In conclusion, we have reported the design and synthesis of a fluorene-based fluorescent receptor 1 for the selective sensing of Hg^{2+} in $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (10 : 1 v/v) medium at pH 7.0 (HEPES buffer, 10 mM).

Experimental

General :

Unless otherwise mentioned, materials were obtained from commercial suppliers and were used without further purification. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was carried out using Merck 60 F₂₅₄ plates with a thickness of 0.25 mm. Melting points were determined on a hot-plate melting point apparatus in an open-mouth capillary and are uncorrected. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 500 MHz instrument. The abbreviation used to represent the multiplicity of the signals is : s (singlet), bs (broad singlet), m (multiplet). For NMR spectra, CDCl_3 was used as a solvent using TMS as an internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ units and $^1\text{H}-^1\text{H}$ and C-C coupling constants in Hz. IR spectra was recorded on a JASCO FT/IR-460 plus spectrometer, using CHCl_3 as solvent.

Fig. 4. (a) Plot of ratio of concentration of guest and host with ratio of initial intensity and final intensity; (b) Job plot between receptor 1 and Hg^{2+} in $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (10 : 1 v/v) medium. The concentration of $[\text{HG}]$ was calculated by the equation $[\text{HG}] = \Delta I/I_0 \times [\text{H}]$; (c) The plot of percentage of quantum yield (receptor 1 and 1-Hg^{2+} complex) vs $[\text{G}]$, concentration of guest Hg^{2+} .

All the metal ions have been used as their perchlorate salts for binding purpose and these perchlorate salts have either been synthesized in our laboratory following the standard procedure or purchased from Sigma-Aldrich company.

Fig. 5. Fluorescence response of receptor 1 towards metal ions upon addition of 25 micro molar solutions of individual metal ions.

Fig. 6. (a) Energy minimized structures (space-filled model) of receptor 1; (b) Its complex with Hg^{2+} by MM2 method.

Synthesis of receptor 1 :

Preparation of compound A :

9-Fluorenone (500 mg, 2.78 mmol) and ethanolamine (170 mg, 2.78 mmol) were subjected to reflux for 1 h in dry EtOH. After completion of the reaction, ethanol was

evaporated and the crude product obtained was purified by column chromatography (100–200 mesh silica gel) using petroleum ether, followed by chloroform as eluent to get the slight yellowish solid compound **A** (480 mg, yield 79%) which is used for the next step, m.p. 86–88 °C.

Preparation of compound **B** :

Compound **A** (450 mg, 2.02 mmol) was treated with sodium borohydride in dry methanol, to furnish the crude product **B** which was further purified by column chromatography with chloroform as eluent to obtain yellowish solid compound **B** (420 mg, yield 92%), m.p. 124–126 °C.

Preparation of compound **C** :

Compound **B** (410 mg, 1.82 mmol) was tosylated in the usual way to compound **C** (610 mg, yield 96%) after successive washing with petroleum ether to remove the excess *p*-TsCl and *p*-TsOH present as impurity, m.p. 78–80 °C.

Preparation of receptor **1** :

To a solution of NaOEt in dry EtOH 1,3-propane dithiol (~0.02 ml, 0.29 mmol) was added dropwise and stirred for 1 h. Then a solution of compound **C** (200 mg, 0.58 mmol) in dry EtOH was added slowly to it and the solution stirred at r.t. for another 2 h. Progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the resulting crude product was purified to afford reddish brown low melting solid **1** (210 mg, yield 70%), m.p. 54–56 °C.

N-(2-(3-(2-(9*H*-Fluoren-9-ylamino)ethylthio)propylthio)ethyl)-9*H*-fluoren-9-amine (Receptor **1**) : ¹H NMR (CDCl₃; 500 MHz) : δ (ppm) 7.67–7.66 (4H, m), 7.54–7.47 (8H, m), 7.31–7.28 (4H, m), 2.81–2.73 (8H, m), 2.62–2.59 (4H, m), 2.11 (2H, s), 1.88–1.92 (4H, m); mass (HRMS) of receptor **1** : mass calcd. for C₃₃H₃₄N₂S₂ is 523.7845 [M+H]⁺ and found 523.7822.

General method of titration :

UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-530 spectrophotometer using a dissolution cell of 10 mm path and the fluorescence spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer LS-55 spectrophotometer using a fluorescence cell (10 mm), respectively. For UV-Vis and fluorescence titration, stock solution of receptor **1** was prepared (*c* = 1.92 × 10⁻⁵ ML⁻¹) in CH₃CN-H₂O (10 : 1 v/v) in the presence of HEPES buffer solution (pH 7.4, 10 mM). The solution of guest anions in the order of 6.88 × 10⁻⁴

was also prepared in CH₃CN-H₂O (10 : 1 v/v). Solutions of various concentrations containing host and increasing concentrations of ions were prepared separately. The spectra of these solutions were recorded by UV-Vis and fluorescence methods.

Binding constant determination by UV-Vis method :

Binding constant by UV-Vis method was calculated according to the Benesi-Hildebrand equation. *K*_a was calculated following the equation stated below.

$$1/(A - A_0) = 1/\{K(A_{\max} - A_0) [M^{X+}]^n\} + 1/[A_{\max} - A_0]$$

Here *A*₀ is the absorbance of receptor **1** in the absence of guest, *A* is the absorbance recorded in the presence of added guest, *A*_{max} is absorbance in the presence of added [Mⁿ⁺]_{max} and *K* is the association constant. The association constant (*K*) was determined from the slope of the straight line of the plot of 1/(*A* - *A*₀) against 1/[M^{X+}] and expressed in the unit M⁻¹. *K*_a determined by UV method of **1** and Hg is 1.29 × 10⁴ M⁻¹.

Linearity of this plot confirms a 1 : 1 complex formation between the receptor **1** and Hg²⁺. This further corroborates a 1 : 1 complex formation that we have concluded based on the spectral titration profile.

By fluorescence method :

The binding constant value of Hg²⁺ with receptor **1** has been determined from the emission intensity data following the modified Benesi-Hildebrand equation^{3,2b}.

$$1/\Delta I = 1/\Delta I_{\max} + (1/K[C])(1/\Delta I_{\max})$$

Here Δ*I* = *I* - *I*_{min} and Δ*I*_{max} = *I*_{max} - *I*_{min}, where *I*_{min}, *I* and *I*_{max} are the emission intensities of receptor **1** considered in the absence of Hg²⁺, at an intermediate Hg²⁺ concentration, and at a concentration of complete saturation where *K* (in M⁻¹) is the binding constant and [*C*] the Hg²⁺ concentration. From the plot of (*I*_{max} - *I*_{min})/(*I* - *I*_{min}) against [*C*]⁻¹ for receptor **1**, the value of *K* has been determined from the slope. *K*_a determined by fluorescence method between **1** and Hg is 1.04 × 10⁴ M⁻¹.

Supporting Information available (¹H NMR, ¹³C spectra, HRMS spectra of receptor **1**).

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